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**“SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION
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SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN INDONESIA

- ◆ *Talkshow Smart Education*
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Opportunities and Challenges for Smart City in Papua Province to realize Papua, Awakening, Independent, Prosperous and Equitable

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Abstract. Papua Province is located at the eastern end of the territory of Indonesia, with a large area and potential for natural resources of economic and strategic value. Smart City itself becomes a part of implementation Internet of things (IoT) in Indonesian. There are three objects of the Smartcity program, namely the community, the government, and city infrastructure. Every city in Indonesia has different problems to apply Smart City. An appropriate way is also needed to integrate the community, government and city infrastructure which is the object of a Smart City. An appropriate way is also needed to integrate the community, government and city infrastructure which is the object of a Smart City. This study discusses the smart city concept and how the challenges and implementation in Papua. The method used in this paper is qualitative. *Smart City* aims to integrate information from the three objects above in order to create an efficient service to realize Papua Awakening, Independent, Prosperous and Equitable.

Keywords: Opportunities, Challenges, Smart City, Papua Provinces, Infrastructure.

PRELIMINARY

The Government System of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia according to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia recognizes and respects special or special regional government units. What is meant by special regional government units are regions that are granted special autonomy.

The regions that are granted special autonomy include:

1. The Province of the Special Capital City Region of Jakarta is enacted by Law Number 29 of 2007 concerning the Provincial Government of the Special Capital City Region of Jakarta as the Capital of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.
2. The Province of Nangro Aceh Darussalam (NAD) was enacted by Law Number 44 of 1999 concerning the Implementation of the Privileges of the Province of the Special Region of Aceh and Law Number 11 of 2006 concerning the Government of Aceh and
3. Papua Province and West Papua Province, Law No. 21 of 2001 concerning Special Autonomy for Papua Province (LN 2001 No. 135 TLN No. 4151) was enacted. The basic things that become the contents of this Law are:
 - a. First, the regulation of authority between the Government and the Papua Provincial Government and the implementation of such authority in the Papua Province which is carried out with specificity;
 - b. Second, recognition and respect for the basic rights of indigenous Papuans and their strategic and fundamental empowerment; and
 - c. Third, realizing good governance with the following characteristics: Maximum people's participation in planning, implementing dan supervising government administration and development implementation through the participation of representatives of adat, religion and women;
 - d. Fourth, the division of authority, duties, and responsibilities is firm and clear between the legislative, executive and judicial bodies, as well as the Papuan People's Assembly as the cultural representation of the indigenous Papuans who are given certain powers.

Figure 1. Map of Papua Province
Source. RPJMD Papua

Papua Province is located at the eastern end of the Indonesian territory, with an area of 420,540 km, as well as the potential for natural resources of economic and strategic value, consisting of indigenous tribal groups in Papua consisting of 255 tribes. Papua's development priorities with the approach of the Independent and Just Prosperous Movement for 2018-2023 are carried out in 28 regencies and 1 city spread over 5 (five) customary areas in Papua. The strategic issues of sustainable development that are formulated are as follows:

1. Quality of life
2. Food security, social and culture
3. Local economy and sustainable natural resource management
4. Destruction of forests and the environment
5. Governance and law enforcement

The synthesis is carried out by adjusting the strategic issues that have been generated with sustainable development goals, especially the targets set by the TPB itself. Several issues are separated so that there is an emphasis on fulfillment whose urgency is quite large based on the level of achievement. Based on the results of the synthesis above, there are 10 priority strategic issues for sustainable development as follows:

1. Population administration
2. Access to clean water and proper sanitation
3. Access to health services
4. Access to education
5. Local economy and sustainable resource management
6. Destruction of forests and the environment
7. Energy resistance
8. Food security
9. Empowerment of women and protection of children
10. Governance and law enforcement

From the results of the KLHS, the TPB that needs to be strengthened in program planning based on strategic issues are as follows;

- a. Maintain and improve transparency, accountability, law enforcement and coordination (governance) of the Environment and Natural Resources; (13, 14, 15, 16);
- b. Ensure that the Papuan people, especially OAP receive proper and adequate education, proper quality of sanitation and clean water, good nutrition and environmental health, equitable development and development;
- c. Inclusive Human Resources (TPB: 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 10);

The purpose of the formulation of regional development problems is to identify various factors that influence the success/failure of regional development performance in the past. *Smart City* itself is a part of the implementation of the Internet of things (IoT) in Indonesia. There are three

objects of the *Smartcity* program , namely the community, government, and city infrastructure. Every city in Indonesia has different problems to apply Smart City. There is also a need for an appropriate way to integrate the community, government and city infrastructure that is the object of a *Smart City* . This study discusses the smart city concept and the challenges and implementation in Papua. The method used in this writing is a literature study. *Smart City* aims to integrate information from the three objects above in order to create an efficient service.

FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

1. What are the problems/issues of the development of the Papua Province?
2. What are the challenges and opportunities for implementing a smart city in Papua Province?

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Suhono (2015), *Smart City* is the development and management of cities by utilizing Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to connect, monitor and control various resources in the city more effectively and efficiently to maximize services to its citizens and support sustainable development. sustainable or in other words a city that knows the problems that exist in it (*sensing*), understands the conditions of the problem (*understanding*), and can regulate (*controlling*) various existing resources to be used effectively and efficiently with the aim of maximizing services to its citizens. The following are some of the components in implementing a smart city.

Table 1 Components of *Smart City*

<i>Smart Living</i>	<i>Smart Environment</i>
Easy access to education services	IT-based environmental management
Easy access to health services	IT-based natural resource management
Media role development	Development of renewable energy sources
Easy access to security guarantees	
Smart Infrastruktur	Smart Governance
IT network development	Pengembangan e-governance
IT-based transport development	Ada partisipasi masyarakat dalam perencanaan Pembangunan
Management information system development, IT based	
Smart Ekonomi	Smart People
City branding development	Education and development of literate human resources
Entrepreneurship development	Technology
E- commerce development	Research support
	Development of the socio-cultural character of the community

Another concept of *Smart Government* is transparency, which is bringing the public closer to government employees. Complaints to the government and giving reputation to regional officials can be done directly through online applications, in addition to the convenience of public services and licensing.

The definition of e-government according to The World Bank Group is an effort to use information and communication technology to improve efficiency and effectiveness, transparency and government accountability in providing better public services (Suaedi, Falih, Wardiyanto, 2010). The Presidential Instruction No. 3 of 2003 concerning the National Policy and Strategy for the Development of E-Government explains that e-government is an effort to develop electronic-based governance in order to improve the quality of public services effectively and efficiently (Aslamaturrahmah, Putri & Darmawan, 2018). Through the development of e-government,

management systems and work processes are arranged in the government environment by optimizing the use of information technology (Tasmil, 2013).

Information Technology and *Good Governance*. In relation to good governance, the development of information technology should also be followed by improving the quality of information technology-based public services, because if this is not done, the government will find it difficult to meet the demands of the public in terms of services they want. services that are faster, more effective, efficient and transparent. In simple terms, *e-government* can be interpreted as a process of service and government management with the help of the use of ICT-based electronic devices. The general purpose of implementing *e-government* is to make the government system more efficient, transparent, and effective. Thus, public service processes such as licensing, payments, and budgeting do not have to be face-to-face. The process becomes faster, transparent, and can be tracked if there is a delay or abuse of authority. In *Smart Government*, public services are carried out centrally, the service system is integrated. The impact is that the system in *Smart Government* can effectively support and ensure easy access to services.

METHODOLOGI

To answer and explain the research formulation above, the method used in this research is normative juridical research, which is *library research*, namely through library data collection.

DISCUSSION

1. Efforts made by Papua Province Towards Smart City

The Papua Provincial Government is implementing various e-government applications to improve the quality of public services and government administration work processes so that they are more effective, efficient, transparent and accountable, as an absolute requirement for the realization of the principles of good and clean governance. In 2017, for example, the Papua Provincial Government has implemented an Online Planning and Budgeting System which consists of 3 parts, namely: e-Musrenbang, e-Planning and e-Budgeting. The e-government application includes three systems, namely planning and budgeting, investment licensing, and local revenue. The planning system consists of e-PapuaPuMusrenbang, e-PapuaPuRencana, and e-PapuaPuAnggaran. The investment licensing system is through e-Papua Online Licensing and the regional income system through e-Samsat. With e-government, it can prevent illegal levies in public services. It is also targeted that local revenue (PAD) reaches Rp 1 trillion after a year of using this application, which functions to integrate local government planning and budgeting. In addition, an online licensing system called e-Papua is also implemented, to provide business licensing services to the private sector online. There is also an online regional revenue system called e-SAMSAT which is used to pay vehicle taxes online and there are many more applications that are implemented in various Regional Apparatus Organizations (Papua Provincial Government Website, 2017). The use of several e-government applications shows that the Papuan provincial government has implemented e-government to support government business processes and public services. Here are some e-Government Applications in Papua Province.

a. E-Musrenbang, Development Planning Consultation Information System

Information System for online Musrenbang (Development Planning) process management. The E-Musrenbang is integrated with the E-Planning System so that the output from the Musrenbang will be entered into the RKPD automatically. E-Musrenbang can be accessed by: Public, District, DPRD, OPD and Bappeda.

Benefits of e-Musrenbang, including:

1. Creating **harmony between** village/sub-district musrenbang proposals with regional priorities.
2. Make it **easier for** sub-districts to submit proposals for activities in Musrenbang.
3. Become a means to facilitate bottom up (participatory), top down (technocratic) planning.
4. Facilitate Regional Apparatus Organizations (OPD) in **verifying** and correcting incoming proposals.
5. Make the e-musrenbang process **on time** according to the implementation schedule.

6. Facilitate the members of the council to convey the **main ideas of the** results of the DPRD recess.
 7. Avoid duplication of proposals at the same location through proposal mapping.
 8. The creation of **transparency** and accountability of the development proposal process.
 9. **Ease** of doing **tracking** against any proposal that goes on every stage.
- b. E-Planning Application, Integrated Regional Development Planning System

Figure 2. Papua e-Government Application
Integrated Regional Development Planning System
Source. Papua Provincial Government Website

The E-Planning application or the Regional Development Planning Information System facilitates Bappeda and SKPD in the preparation of work programs. So that development planning can run effectively, efficiently and integrated. E-Planning is a tool for Bappeda in planning, controlling and evaluating the implementation of regional development plans.

Some of the Benefits of Implementing E-Planning Applications:

1. The preparation of the Regional Development Work Plan (RKPD) can be done on-line.
2. **Integrated** database, Planning data is used for other system data.
3. Gradual Timing, so that the preparation of the RKPD can run on time .
4. **Monitoring** Budget Absorption Becomes Easier.
5. Supports Single Sign On (One Login to Multiple Systems).
6. The Planning Process Becomes Practical and Easy .

The Papuan Provincial Government in August 2021 launched a website application program aimed at empowering the community, as well as encouraging contributions to Papua's progress through the economy, which helps people who are currently "warring" against the COVID-19 pandemic. The two websites are the Application System for Supervision of the National Economic Recovery Program (SIAP WAROPEN) and the credit for the Regional Financial Access Acceleration Program (PAPEDA).

2. Opportunities and Challenges for the Development of Papua Province Towards a *Smart City*.
With the existence of special autonomy in Papua Province, there is a greater chance of a *smart city* because;
 1. Development priorities are determined by the regions.
 2. Regional development is more advanced, by giving rights and authority from the regional government to parts that are currently abundant in resources and meeting market needs, it is also possible that the region will be more developed.
 3. Regional management based on its potential is also regulated in its income and expenditure in accordance with the Regional Budget (Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget).
 4. Local governments are easy to adapt to the special needs of the region with the existence of regional autonomy.
 5. Local governments are easier to adapt to the special needs of the region with the existence of regional autonomy.

6. Initially, the internet network infrastructure in the government and internet cafe businesses used the VSAT network so that it was often disrupted. However, with the construction program of the Palapa Ring (underwater fiber optic network) carried out by PT. Telkom and has entered Papua since 2014, the community and local government increasingly feel the ease of access to telecommunications

The challenges of implementing Regional Governments related to special autonomy include:

1. Regulatory conflicts.
2. Supervision is weak from the central government to local governments.
3. The local government has not yet actualized the development of the leading sector according to the characteristics, peculiarities and optimal potential of the region's superiority.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Smart city concept (*Smart City*) that helps the community by managing existing resources efficiently and providing the right information to the community or anticipating unexpected events. SmartCity can be concluded that utilizing information resources and using sophisticated technology to make life easier. *Smart Government* must be able to maintain and improve the ease of all-in-one access. No more confusion, long queues at various government agencies, and filling out paper forms for sheets. One of the answers to face challenges in the technological era is the development of a technology-based government system known as *e-government*. Papua Province already has e-planning and e-budgeting integrated with the Ministry of Home Affairs' SIPD application. With *e-government*, the allocation of 80 percent of special autonomy funds to 28 districts and 1 city can be monitored properly. Officials in the regions also cannot change the budget plan arbitrarily.

References

- Bappenas, 2015. National Framework for Smart City Development in Indonesia, Jakarta.
- Bappeda DIY, 2015. Smart City Challenges for Yogyakarta Bedudaya. Exposure, Yogyakarta.
- E-Government Application Blueprint, Jakarta: Ministry of Communication and Informatics, 2004
- Document BP3TI KPU/OSO Program Ministry of Communication and Informatics, 2014
- Damanik. The City Government of Pekanbaru City Government Strategic Plan for EGovernment Development. Thesis: MTI UGM Yogyakarta, 2008
- Economics and Social Council, 2016, Smart Cities and Infrastructure,
- Indrajit, Richardus Eko, Conceptual Framework for the Master Plan for Corporate Information Systems, Journal of Information Systems, MTI-UI, vol.1, no.1, pp. 11-17, September 2005
- 6 Smart City Indicators, Community and Government Play Important Roles <https://inixindojogja.co.id/6-indikator-smart-city- Masyarakat-dan-governmental-berperan-penting/> (accessed September 2, 2021)
- Getting to Know the Smart City Concept in City Development <https://aptika.kominfo.go.id/2020/10/menkenal-more-close-concept-smart-city-dalam-pembinaan-kota/> (accessed September 2, 2021)
- Papua Province Medium Term Development Plan 2013-2018
- Supangkat, Suhono. 2015. Anatomy of the City and Smart City, Indonesia Smart city Initiatives
- Sugiyono, Qualitative Quantitative Research Methods and R&D, Alfabeta, Bandung, December 2012
- <https://disdukcapil.pontianakkota.go.id/mengbangun-smart-government-dalam-meningkatkan-pelayan-publik-ditulis-by-christian-tobing>
- <https://www.boyyendratamin.com/2011/12/autonomi-special-di-indonesia.html>
- <https://www.integraindonesia.co.id/e-musrenbang/>
- <https://ppr.papua.go.id/2021/landing/>
- <https://jubi.co.id/pemprov-papua-raih-penghargaan-integration-e-planing-sipd/>
- <https://www.kompas.id/baca/nusantara/2017/03/09/papua-mulai-apply-e-government/>

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